

ECONOSCITECH INTEGRATION

ISSUE
6

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC
ELECTRONIC JOURNAL

TASHKENT STATE
UNIVERSITY OF ECONOMICS

American University
of Technology

Powered by Arizona State University®

ISSN: 3060-5075

Acceptance of articles
PUBLISHED MONTHLY

ARTICLE CONTRIBUTORS
PROFESSORS, SCHOLARS,
SPECIALISTS, AND RESEARCHERS

Google
Scholar

Academic
Resource
Index
ResearchBib

BASE

OpenAIRE

doi
Digital
Object
Identifier

OPEN ACCESS

CONTACT:

+998 94 3540880

<https://econoscitech-integration-journal.uz>

2026

EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Zufarova Nozima Gulamiddinovna
DSc., Dean of Tourism Faculty, TSUE

DEPUTY EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Makhmudov Nosir Makhmudovich
DSc., Prof., Academician

DEPUTY EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Suyunov Dilmurod Xolmurodovich
Doctor of Economics (DSc), Professor,

DEPUTY EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Allayarov Shamsiddin Amanullayevich
doctor of economics (DSC), professor

RESPONSIBLE SECRETARY:

Otaboyev Axmed Maxsudbek o'g'li
TSUE independent researcher

THE SCIENTIFIC-POPULAR
ELECTRONIC JOURNAL
"ECONOSCITECH-INTEGRATION"
HAS BEEN REGISTERED UNDER
THE NUMBER C-5669651 BY THE
AGENCY FOR INFORMATION AND
MASS COMMUNICATIONS (AOKA)
OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN,
EFFECTIVE FROM OCTOBER 9, 2024.

In accordance with Resolution No. 384/6 dated April 10, 2026, issued by the Presidium of the Supreme Attestation Commission under the Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, this journal is included in the list of recommended international scientific publications for publishing the primary research findings of doctoral dissertations in the field of Economic Sciences.

Partners: Tashkent State University of Economics / American University of Technology in Tashkent (AUT)

Electronic publication, Issue 6. 374 pages.
Approved for publication on Iyun, 2026.

Editorial Board Members:

Sharipov Kongratbay Avezimbetovich,
Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor

Teshabayev To'liqin Zakirovich,
Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Said Irandoust,
Doctor of Chemical Engineering Sciences,
Professor

Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna,
Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Khudoykulov Sadirdin Karimovich,
Doctor of Economics, (DSc), Professor

Tokunaga Masahiro,
professor, PhD of Economics of the Faculty of
Business and Commerce

Debasis Das,
professor Department of Computer Science

Nitin Goje,
professor and Program Lead - Computer Science

Nargizakhon Shamshieva
Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor

Rakhmonov Norim Razzakovich,
Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Bayxonov Bahodirjon Tursunbayevich
Doctor of Science (DSc), Professor

Shomurodov Ravshan Tursunkulovich,
PhD, Associate Professor

Boymuratov Abduraxmat Djumayevich
Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics

Sharopova Nafosat Radjabovna
DSc, Associate Professor

Sultanova Kamila Mukhtorali Kizi
Master of Science

CONTENTS

MECHANISMS FOR IMPLEMENTING TECHNOLOGICAL AND DIGITAL INNOVATIONS.....	10
Shakirxodjayeva Zuxra Rustamxanovna	
DEVELOPMENT OF ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC MECHANISMS FOR IMPROVING INVESTMENT PROCESSES IN THE CONSTRUCTION INDUSTRY	16
Aliyeva Zilola Mamatvalyevna	
CURRENT STATE AND STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF SERVICE SECTORS IN TASHKENT CITY.....	23
Abdikayumov Bekzod Turdiniyozovich	
GREEN BONDS VS. SUSTAINABILITY LINKED LOANS: WHICH WORKS FOR INDUSTRIAL DECARBONISATION?	29
Ataxanov Umidbek Olimovich	
ИНТЕГРИРОВАННАЯ МОДЕЛЬ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ БЕЗОПАСНОСТЬЮ БАНКА.....	34
Маликова Дилрабо Муминовна	
ECONOMETRIC MODELLING OF FAMILY ENTREPRENEURSHIP DEVELOPMENT IN THE TOURISM SECTOR: EVIDENCE FROM UZBEKISTAN	42
Pardayeva Ozoda Mamayunusovna	
AN INTEGRAL INDEX METHODOLOGY FOR ASSESSING THE INVESTMENT POTENTIAL OF AGRICULTURAL ENTERPRISES	49
Sayyora Bakhtiyorovna Nazirova	
ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫЕ, ПУБЛИЧНЫЕ И ОБЩЕСТВЕННЫЕ ФИНАНСЫ В УСЛОВИЯХ ЦИФРОВОЙ ТРАНСФОРМАЦИИ: ТЕРМИНОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ГРАНИЦЫ И ИНСТИТУЦИОНАЛЬНАЯ ЭВОЛЮЦИЯ.....	53
Срождиддинова Зарина Хайриддиновна	
BLOCKCHAIN-BASED FINANCIAL TRANSACTION MONITORING SYSTEM (SMART CONTRACTS, DECENTRALIZED DATABASE, AND AUDIT TRAILS).....	58
Olimova Mukhlisa Vohidjon qizi	
FAMILY ENTREPRENEURSHIP AS A DRIVER OF EMPLOYMENT IN THE TOURISM SECTOR: REGIONAL DISPARITIES AND INSTITUTIONAL MECHANISMS IN UZBEKISTAN.....	65
Pardayeva Ozoda Mamayunusovna	
ANALYSIS OF THE MAIN STATISTICAL INDICATORS OF LABOR RESOURCE UTILIZATION IN SURXONDARYO REGION.....	72
Haydarova Dinora Atamurot qizi	
ASSESSING THE ROLE OF SPECIAL ECONOMIC ZONES IN REGIONAL ECONOMIC GROWTH ACROSS THE REGIONS OF UZBEKISTAN USING INTENSITY COEFFICIENTS AND CLUSTER ANALYSIS.....	77
Anvarkhonov Abdulatifkhon Jamshidkhon ugli	
TECHNICAL, ECONOMIC, AND ENVIRONMENTAL EFFICIENCY OF IMPLEMENTING AGRIVOLTAIC SYSTEMS IN UZBEKISTAN	85
Jabborov Shaymurod Akram o'g'li	
Botirov Bozorbek Musurmon o'g'li	
Atoyeva Mohinur Amrilloevna	
Avazov Jonibek Azizbek o'g'li	
МОДЕЛИРОВАНИЕ ВЛИЯНИЯ ЧЕЛОВЕЧЕСКОГО КАПИТАЛА НА ТРАЕКТОРИЮ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО РОСТА.....	91

Хазраткулова Лола Нармуминовна FINANCING GREEN PROJECTS IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN: STATUS, CHALLENGES AND PROSPECTS	97
Qorriyeva Shahnoza Safarbayevna	
FORMULA-BASED DISTRIBUTION OF INTERGOVERNMENTAL TRANSFERS TO LOCAL BUDGETS IN UZBEKISTAN: A COMPARATIVE SIMULATION ANALYSIS BASED ON 2026 FORECAST INDICATORS.....	103
Umidjon Pardaev Sarvar Maxmudov	
GOVERNMENT FUNDING AND THE DEVELOPMENT OF INNOVATIVE ACTIVITIES: FINANCIAL PROMOTION MECHANISMS	115
Bahriddinov Nodirbek Zamirdinovich	
FORECASTING EXPORT AND IMPORT INDICATORS OF BUKHARA REGION	122
Ergashev Mirjon Yorqin o'g'li	
A CUSTOMER-ORIENTED INTEGRATIVE METHODOLOGICAL MODEL FOR IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF TOURIST SERVICES IN THE TOURISM AND HOSPITALITY INDUSTRY	130
Bakayev Ziyovuddinkhan Toshbolta ogli	
A PESTLI ANALYSIS OF THE EFFICIENCY OF THE HOUSING STOCK MANAGEMENT SYSTEM	139
Mamanazarov Oybek Shomurodovich	
ANALYSIS OF THE DEVELOPMENT STATUS AND EXPORT ACTIVITIES OF SMALL BUSINESS AND PRIVATE ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN UZBEKISTAN	146
Khikmatullayeva Nargiza Jamoliddin kizi	
CHANGE MANAGEMENT DURING QUALITY ASSURANCE REFORM IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS	154
Urinov Bobur Nasilloevich	
СТРАТЕГИИ УСТОЙЧИВОГО РАЗВИТИЯ ПАЛОМНИЧЕСКОГО ТУРИЗМА В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ	162
Каримова Дилафруз Садриддин кизи	
E-COMMERCE AS A DIGITAL FORM OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN INCREASING HOUSEHOLD INCOMES	167
Eshbayeva Shahnoza Fakhriddinovna	
ADVANTAGES OF IMPLEMENTING AN OCCUPATIONAL AND SKILLS MAPPING SYSTEM IN UZBEKISTAN'S LABOUR MARKET	172
S.B.Goyipnazarov S.M.Kurbanbaeva	
ASSESSMENT OF THE EFFICIENCY OF FIXED ASSETS UTILIZATION IN RAILWAY ENTERPRISES: EVIDENCE FROM UZBEKISTAN.....	178
Turdiyeva Irodaxon Ismoil qizi	
SCIENTIFIC AND METHODOLOGICAL APPROACHES TO ASSESSING RESOURCE USE IN THE CONTEXT OF A GREEN ECONOMY.....	183
Karimov Islombek Bekpolat o'g'li	
THE IMPACT OF ECOTOURISM ON REGIONAL ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT	
Samiev Siroj Saitovich Ochilova Guli Rashid kizi	
THE IMPACT OF RISK ALLOCATION ON INVESTMENT EFFICIENCY IN PUBLIC- PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP (PPP) PROJECTS	197
Khaydarova Charos Nizomiddinovna	

PROSPECTS FOR CHANGING THE VOLUME OF GRAPE CULTIVATION DUE TO THE USE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE VITICULTURE COMPLEX.....	202
Boltaev Nazarbek Narzullaevich	
ЦИФРОВЫЕ МЕХАНИЗМЫ ОБОСНОВАНИЯ НАЧАЛЬНОЙ ЦЕНЫ В ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫХ ЗАКУПКАХ: ПРОЗРАЧНОСТЬ, КОНКУРЕНЦИЯ И РАЦИОНАЛЬНОЕ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ СРЕДСТВ.....	209
Тўхтасинов Бобомурод Исақжон ўғли	
ENHANCING FOREIGN DIRECT INVESTMENT INFLOWS IN THE POST-CRISIS ERA: AN ECONOMETRIC ANALYSIS OF UZBEKISTAN.....	215
Foziljon Rustamov Hazratkulovich	
CURRENT STATE AND DEVELOPMENT TRENDS OF THE TEXTILE INDUSTRY.....	219
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna	
ITHE PECULIARITIES OF USING FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF TOURIST AND RECREATIONAL AREAS.....	225
Makhliyo Umarova	
CHALLENGES OF ATTRACTING INVESTMENTS IN HUMAN CAPITAL AND STRATEGIES FOR THEIR RESOLUTION.....	231
Aloviddin Zayniddinov Zayniddin ugli	
ANALYSIS OF THE EXPERIENCE OF SUCCESSFUL AGROTOURISM DESTINATIONS IN DIFFERENT COUNTRIES: RECOMMENDATIONS FOR UZBEKISTAN.....	237
Aktamov Olimjon Abdugani o'g'li	
ASSESSING THE EFFICIENCY OF STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT OF EDUCATIONAL SERVICES EXPORT AT THE REGIONAL LEVEL.....	247
Alimova Shamsiya Abidovna	
ECONOMIC ESSENCE OF THE EXPORT POTENTIAL OF BUSINESS ENTITIES AND CLASSIFICATION OF THE FACTORS SHAPING IT: THE CASE OF BUKHARA REGION.....	254
Djurayeva Munira Sadillovovna	
THE ROLE OF INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES IN THE ECONOMY OF BUKHARA REGION AND THEIR DEVELOPMENT TRENDS: AN ANALYSIS OF STRUCTURAL CHANGES AND REGIONAL CONCENTRATION.....	261
Azizjon Anvarovich Kadirov	
Nigina Djurayevna Yusupova	
IMPROVING THE ECONOMIC MECHANISMS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF BORDER TRANSPORT SYSTEMS.....	268
Ikromov Elyor Ibodulloevich	
ПУТИ ИНТЕГРАЦИИ НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ И МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫХ СТАНДАРТОВ АУДИТОРСКОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ.....	273
Бобонарова Камола	
GREEN BONDS AND SOVEREIGN DEBT INSTRUMENTS FOR INFRASTRUCTURE ASSET RENEWAL: AN ANALYSIS OF FINANCIAL MECHANISMS.....	278
Suleimanov Farrukh	
ENHANCING THE COMPETITIVENESS OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF INTERNATIONAL AND NATIONAL EXPERIENCES.....	286
Qudratova Gulzoda Mahmudovna	
THE ROLE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION SERVICES IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY.....	291
Munisa Abdurakhmonova	
ECONOMETRIC MODELING OF REGIONAL ECONOMIC GROWTH BASED ON THE COBBDOUGLAS PRODUCTION FUNCTION: A CASE STUDY OF SURXONDARYA REGION.....	296

Turaev Bakhtiyor Ergashevich	
GENERAL APPROACHES TO COST REDUCTION IN THE TEXTILE INDUSTRY	302
Kamola Saidova	
СОВРЕМЕННОЕ СОСТОЯНИЕ ПЛАНИРОВАНИЯ И ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ ВНУТРЕННЕГО АУДИТА В БЮДЖЕТНЫХ ОРГАНИЗАЦИЯХ.....	307
Саитмуратов Саитмурат Машарип угли	
A CONCEPTUAL MODEL OF THE IMPACT OF INTERMEDIATION SERVICES ON BANK PERFORMANCE AND ITS STATISTICAL RESEARCH METHODOLOGY	314
Miraxmedov Jasur Isroilovich	
EMPLOYER BRANDING IN UZBEKISTAN: HOW TO BECOME AN EMPLOYER OF CHOICE FOR TALENT	320
Doniyorova Fotimabonu Alisher qizi	
FORMING THE COMMUNICATIVE CULTURE OF MANAGING PERSONNEL AND STUDENTS BASED ON A COMPETENCY-BASED APPROACH.....	325
Temirova Shakhlo Rakhmonovna	
MODERN APPROACHES TO FORMING A COMMUNICATIVE CULTURE OF STUDENTS OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS.....	331
Temirova Shakhlo Rakhmonovna	
IMPROVEMENT OF THE SYSTEM OF ACCOUNTING AND ANALYSIS OF MATERIAL COSTS IN OIL AND GAS INDUSTRY ENTITIES BASED ON MODERN MANAGEMENT REQUIREMENTS.....	336
Sa'dullayeva Sayyora Nasillo qizi	
ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC APPROACHES AND BARRIERS TO THE INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN	341
Samieva Gulnoza Tokhirovna	
THE IMPACT OF EFFECTIVE UTILIZATION OF LABOR POTENTIAL ON THE SUSTAINABLE ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF A REGION (A case study of the Khorezm region).....	348
Kutlimuratov Mansurbek Sattarovich	
CHARACTERISTICS OF CLUSTERING TEXTILE ENTERPRISES.....	354
Asadbek Eshniyozov	
THE ROLE OF EDUCATION AND CAPACITYBUILDING IN DEVELOPING THE ISLAMIC FINANCE INDUSTRY: A THEORETICAL AND COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS	358
Abdullaev Azamat Akbar o'g'li	
THE ROLE OF 5G TECHNOLOGIES IN IMPROVING THE ECONOMIC PERFORMANCE OF TELECOMMUNICATION ENTERPRISES	366
Saidqosimova Umida Ibragimovna	
DIGITAL PLATFORMS AND THE EFFICIENCY OF INCLUSIVE EDUCATION: EVIDENCE FROM UZBEKISTAN	371
Kholmonov Shodiyor Karshiboyevich	
MAIN DIRECTIONS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF INTEREST RATE RISK MANAGEMENT PRACTICES IN COMMERCIAL BANKS OF UZBEKISTAN.....	377
Seitnazarov Daniyar Bakhadyrovich	
METHODOLOGY AND WAYS OF EFFECTIVE MANAGEMENT OF SMALL INDUSTRIAL ZONES.....	385
Shodmonkulov Kamoliddin Murodillayevich	
MAIN DIRECTIONS AND PROSPECTS FOR THE EFFECTIVE MANAGEMENT OF INVESTMENTS IN THE CONTEXT OF TRANSFORMATION	391
To'rayev Jasurali To'rayevich	
IMPROVING THE EFFECTIVE MANAGEMENT OF THE DEVELOPMENT	

OF SMALL INDUSTRIAL ZONES.....	395
Shodmonkulov Kamoliddin Murodillayevich	
ПОВЫШЕНИЕ ИНВЕСТИЦИОННОЙ АКТИВНОСТИ РЕГИОНОВ КАК ФАКТОР ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЯ УСТОЙЧИВОГО ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО РОСТА.....	399
Бутаева Сабина Холиёровна	
THE ROLE OF DIGITAL MARKETING STRATEGIES IN INCREASING THE BRAND CAPITAL OF TOURISM ENTERPRISES	404
Zufarov Akmal Gulamiddinovich	
ANALYSIS OF THE CURRENT STATE OF INFRASTRUCTURE PROJECT FINANCING UNDER PUBLIC-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIPS (PPP)	416
Shodiev Akmal O'ktamjon ugli	
IMPROVING THE MANAGEMENT OF THE INVESTMENT ENVIRONMENT	422
To'rayev Jasurali To'rayevich	
BLOCKCHAIN AND IOT FOR DIGITAL TRACKING OF FOOD EXPORT/IMPORT FLOWS.....	426
Nazarova Ra'no Rustamovna	
Najmiddinov Yakhyo Fazliddin ugli	
THE PAYBACK PERIOD METHOD IN PERSONAL FINANCE: APPLICATIONS AND IMPLICATIONS FOR FINANCIAL DECISION-MAKING	438
Akhunova Elena Anvarovna	
DEVELOPMENT OF AN ADAPTIVE FIBONACCI STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS MODEL FOR GOLD TRADING: EVIDENCE FROM THE XAU/USD MARKET	447
Tukmirzaev Kamol Mumin ugli	
DEVELOPING MARKETING MANAGEMENT IN RETAIL TRADE THROUGH A BRAND MANAGEMENT SYSTEM: DIRECTIONS AND STRATEGIC PRIORITIES.....	455
Shohboz Ro'zimatov Hamdambek o'g'li	
MODERN APPROACHES TO FORMING A COMMUNICATIVE CULTURE OF STUDENTS OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS	461
Temirova Shakhlo Rakhmonovna	
FORMING THE COMMUNICATIVE CULTURE OF MANAGING PERSONNEL AND STUDENTS ON THE BASIS OF A COMPETENCY-BASED APPROACH.....	466
Temirova Shakhlo Rakhmonovna	
ЭВОЛЮЦИЯ НАУЧНЫХ ВЗГЛЯДОВ НА РОЛЬ СФЕРЫ УСЛУГ В ЭКОНОМИКЕ.....	472
Усманов Фарзод Шохрухович	
STRATEGIC INSIGHTS FOR UZBEKISTAN'S RURAL DIGITALIZATION: LESSONS FROM THE SPATIAL SPILLOVER EFFECTS OF CHINA'S DIGITAL ECONOMY	481
Zhang Zhe	
ЦИФРОВЫЕ МЕХАНИЗМЫ ОБОСНОВАНИЯ НАЧАЛЬНОЙ ЦЕНЫ В ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫХ ЗАКУПКАХ: ПРОЗРАЧНОСТЬ, КОНКУРЕНЦИЯ И РАЦИОНАЛЬНОЕ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ СРЕДСТВ	487
Тўхтасинов Бобомурод Исақжон ўғли	
IMPROVING ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC MECHANISMS FOR ENHANCING SERVICE INFRASTRUCTURE EFFICIENCY: EVIDENCE FROM KASHKADARYA REGION	493
Azimov Islom	
ASSESSING DIGITAL GOVERNANCE EFFECTIVENESS IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS: EVIDENCE FROM UZBEKISTAN	498
Berdiyev Temurbek Makhmudullo ugli	
РАЗРАБОТКА ИНТЕГРАЛЬНОГО ИНДЕКСА КОРПОРАТИВНОГО УПРАВЛЕНИЯ (CGI) ДЛЯ БАНКОВ С ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫМ УЧАСТИЕМ.....	506

Жумадуллаева Дурдона Шухрат кизи	
DIGITAL ECONOMY-BASED GOVERNANCE IN HIGHER EDUCATION: LEVERAGING AI AND DATA FOR IMPROVED INSTITUTIONAL PERFORMANCE	512
Olimjonov Abbosjon Olimjonovich	
THE IMPACT OF E-COMMERCE DEVELOPMENT ON NATIONAL ECONOMIC COMPETITIVENESS.....	517
Baymuradov Shokhrukh Makhmudovich	
FACTORS INFLUENCING TAX REVENUE EFFICIENCY IN UZBEKISTAN IN THE CONTEXT OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT.....	522
Jurayev Xusan Atamuratovich	
THE ESSENCE, TASKS, AND INTERNATIONAL APPROACHES OF INTERNAL AUDIT IN LEASING TRANSACTIONS.....	536
Sadritdinov Bakhodir Bakhtiyarovich	
DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION OF MANAGEMENT ACCOUNTING IN THE MINING SECTOR.....	543
Oybekova S.K.	
METHODOLOGY FOR REFLECTING GOODWILL, INTANGIBLE ASSETS, AND INVESTMENTS IN CONSOLIDATION.....	548
Maxmudova Nargiza Davlyat qizi	
FACTORS AFFECTING DAIRY PRODUCTION EFFICIENCY: CORRELATION AND REGRESSION ANALYSIS.....	554
Ergashev M.Y.	
Tairova Z.M.	
THE DMED INFORMATION SYSTEM AS A FOUNDATION FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE NATIONAL E-HEALTH SYSTEM	561
Omonov Olim Murodullayevich	
THEORETICAL AND ECONOMIC FOUNDATIONS FOR ENHANCING THE COMPETITIVENESS OF AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTS IN GLOBAL MARKETS	566
Safarova Muxabbat Radjabovna	
THEORETICAL AND ECONOMIC FOUNDATIONS OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE SUPPLY SYSTEM OF NURSERY FARMS	573
Abdufarmonov Farrux Faxriddinovich	
APPLICATION OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE TOURISM MARKET AND ASSESSMENT OF THE EFFICIENCY OF THE PLATFORM ECONOMY.....	580
Jumayev Bobomurod Nurmaxmat o'g'li	
ОСОБЕННОСТИ «ЖЕНСКОГО» ЧЕЛОВЕЧЕСКОГО КАПИТАЛА В ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ СИСТЕМЕ.....	586
Холбаева Сабина Рустамовна	
ВНЕДРЕНИЕ ПРИОРИТЕТНЫХ НАПРАВЛЕНИЙ ПОДДЕРЖКИ ИННОВАЦИОННОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ С УЧЁТОМ ЗАРУБЕЖНОГО ОПЫТА В МАЛОМ И СРЕДНЕМ БИЗНЕСЕ УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	595
Камбарова Шахнозахон Мирвахитовна	
ISSUES OF EFFECTIVELY UTILIZING REGIONAL EXPORT POTENTIAL IN UZBEKISTAN	603
Umaraliyev Sarvar Rustamovich	
TERRITORIAL DISPROPORTIONS IN TOURISM INFRASTRUCTURE OF THE JIZZAKH REGION AND THEIR IMPACT ON TOURIST FLOWS.....	610
A.Sh. Daliev	
T.Sh. Muxiddinov	

METHODOLOGICAL APPROACHES TO HOUSING CONSTRUCTION DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN: INVESTMENT EFFICIENCY AND PUBLIC-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP MECHANISMS.....	616
Mirumar Abdulla Ugli Usmonov	
IMPROVEMENT OF COST ACCOUNTING AND ECONOMIC ANALYSIS IN THE FISHERY INDUSTRY: PRIORITY DIRECTIONS FOR THE ADAPTATION OF IFRS, ECONOMETRIC MODELING, AND ESG REPORTING FOR FISHERY CLUSTERS IN UZBEKISTAN.....	620
Shodiev Aslam Rakhmatilloevich	
Alikulov Abdumumin Ismatovich	
WAYS TO DEVELOP FRUIT PROCESSING ENTERPRISES BASED ON THE CLUSTER SYSTEM	627
Yusufova Laylo G'ayrat qizi	
ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN MODERN BANKING SERVICE DEVELOPMENT	635
Mamutova Aygul Kalmurzaevna	
IMPLEMENTATION OF COMPUTER-ASSISTED AUDIT TECHNIQUES (CAATS) AND ANALYTICAL PROCEDURES IN THE AUDIT OF COMMERCIAL BANKS' FINANCIAL STATEMENTS.....	642
Ibragimov Nodirbek Baxodir ugli	
CRITERIA FOR ASSESSING THE QUALITY OF THE AUDIT OF COMMERCIAL BANKS' FINANCIAL STATEMENTS AND THE FORMATION OF KEY AUDIT MATTERS (ISA 701)	649
Ibragimov Nodirbek Baxodir ugli	
THE ROLE OF EDUCATION AND CAPACITYBUILDING IN DEVELOPING THE ISLAMIC FINANCE INDUSTRY: A THEORETICAL AND COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS	656
Abdullayev Azamat Akbar o'g'li	

THE ROLE OF EDUCATION AND CAPACITY-BUILDING IN DEVELOPING THE ISLAMIC FINANCE INDUSTRY: A THEORETICAL AND COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

Abdullayev Azamat Akbar o'g'li

Independent Researcher, Department of Economics and Management

Tashkent State University of Economics

E-mail: aa.abdullayev01@gmail.com

Abstract. This article presents a theoretical and comparative analysis of the role of education and capacity-building in the development of the Islamic finance industry. The central argument is that the long-term growth of Islamic finance depends not only on capital, regulation, and product innovation, but also critically on the supply of qualified human capital capable of combining expertise in finance, economics, and Shariah.

While the global Islamic finance industry reached approximately USD 5.98 trillion in assets in 2024, representing a 21% year-on-year increase, and is projected to reach USD 9.7 trillion by 2029, the supply of specialized professionals has lagged behind, resulting in a persistent talent gap. Drawing on the experience of leading jurisdictions such as Malaysia, the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) countries, the United Kingdom, and Indonesia, the article compares two models of human capital formation: the institution-led, centrally coordinated model and the market-led, fragmented model, and evaluates their effectiveness.

The analysis applies human capital theory to the specific knowledge requirements of Islamic financial institutions and identifies education, professional certification, Shariah scholarship development, and research as the four pillars of capacity-building. The findings indicate that a coordinated national education strategy, anchored by a dedicated institution and aligned with industry demand, is the most effective mechanism for closing the talent gap and sustaining industry growth.

Keywords: Islamic finance, human capital, capacity-building, education, professional certification, talent gap, Shariah scholarship, INCEIF, financial literacy, knowledge ecosystem.

Аннотация. В статье представлен теоретический и сравнительный анализ роли образования и развития человеческого потенциала (capacity-building) в развитии индустрии исламских финансов. Основная идея исследования заключается в том, что долгосрочный рост исламской финансовой индустрии определяется не только объемом капитала, качеством регулирования и инновациями финансовых продуктов, но и наличием квалифицированных специалистов, обладающих комплексными знаниями в области финансов, экономики и норм шариата.

Несмотря на то что совокупный объем активов мировой индустрии исламских финансов в 2024 году достиг приблизительно 5,98 трлн долларов США, увеличившись на 21 % по сравнению с предыдущим годом, а к 2029 году, по прогнозам, превысит 9,7 трлн долларов США, подготовка специализированных кадров не успевает за темпами развития отрасли, что обуславливает сохраняющийся дефицит квалифицированных специалистов.

На основе опыта ведущих стран, включая Малайзию, государства Совета сотрудничества арабских государств Персидского залива (GCC), Великобританию и Индонезию, в статье проводится сравнительный анализ двух моделей формирования человеческого капитала: институциональной модели с централизованной координацией и рыночной модели с фрагментированной системой подготовки кадров, а также оценивается их эффективность.

Исследование опирается на теорию человеческого капитала и показывает, что ключевыми элементами развития кадрового потенциала исламской финансовой индустрии являются образование, профессиональная сертификация, подготовка специалистов по шариату и развитие научных исследований. Полученные результаты свидетельствуют о том, что скоординированная национальная стратегия подготовки кадров, основанная на деятельности специализированного образовательного учреждения и ориентированная на реальные потребности отрасли, является наиболее эффективным механизмом сокращения кадрового дефицита и обеспечения устойчивого развития исламской финансовой индустрии.

Ключевые слова: исламские финансы, человеческий капитал, развитие кадрового потенциала, образование, профессиональная сертификация, дефицит квалифицированных кадров, шариатские исследования, INCEIF, финансовая грамотность, экосистема знаний.

INTRODUCTION

Understanding the determinants of growth in any financial industry requires attention not only to capital and regulation but also to the human capital that designs, operates, and governs financial institutions. In the theory of economic growth, human capital, defined as the stock of knowledge, skills, and competencies embodied in the workforce, is recognized as a primary driver of productivity and innovation. The Islamic finance industry, as a relatively young and rapidly expanding sector, is particularly sensitive to the availability and quality of specialized human capital.

In this context, education and capacity-building emerge as strategic priorities rather than peripheral concerns. Islamic finance is, in principle, more complex than its conventional counterpart because every product and transaction must satisfy not only economic and legal criteria but also the requirements of Shariah. This dual compliance requires professionals who combine competence in finance, accounting, and economics with a sound understanding of Islamic commercial jurisprudence (*fiqh al-muamalat*), a combination that conventional education systems rarely produce.

The relevance of this issue is underscored by the scale of the industry. According to the ICD–LSEG Islamic Finance Development Report 2025, global Islamic finance assets reached USD 5.98 trillion in 2024, representing a 21% year-on-year increase, with the industry now present in 140 countries and projected to reach USD 9.7 trillion by 2029 (ICD–LSEG, 2025). Yet industry observers have long warned that the supply of trained professionals has not kept pace. Widely cited projections from the early 2010s estimated the additional global requirement at around 50,000 professionals and the need in the United Arab Emirates alone at roughly 8,000 experts, linked to Dubai’s ambition to become the capital of the global Islamic economy (Gulf News, 2013; DIEDC, 2017). More recent evidence confirms that the shortage persists. In Pakistan, where the courts have mandated a full transition to Islamic banking by 2027, the industry is estimated to require nearly 4,000 additional skilled bankers across almost 5,000 operating branches (IBA CEIF, 2024). This challenge reflects a broader global pattern of structural talent shortages and rapidly changing skill requirements documented across sectors (ManpowerGroup, 2013; World Economic Forum, 2025).

The relevance of this issue is particularly significant for emerging Islamic finance markets, including Uzbekistan, where the legal foundations of Islamic finance have only recently been established and where the domestic supply of qualified professionals remains at an early stage of development. For such markets, the experience of more mature jurisdictions in building education and capacity-building ecosystems offers valuable lessons.

The aim of this research is to analyze, from theoretical and comparative perspectives, the role of education and capacity-building in the development of the Islamic finance industry and to identify the institutional arrangements most conducive to closing the talent gap.

The research pursues five objectives: to clarify the economic nature of human capital and its specific application to Islamic finance; to identify the distinctive knowledge requirements of Islamic financial institutions; to compare alternative models of human capital formation across leading jurisdictions; to examine the four pillars of capacity-building, namely formal education, professional certification, Shariah scholarship development, and research; and to derive practical implications for emerging markets.

The scientific novelty of the study lies in framing education and capacity-building not as a supporting function but as a structural determinant of industry growth. It also demonstrates, through comparative analysis, that the institutional design of the education ecosystem, rather than the sheer volume of training, explains differences in outcomes across jurisdictions.

LITERATURE REVIEW

One of the central concepts of modern growth economics is human capital theory, developed by Schultz (1961) and Becker (1964), which treats education and training as investments that increase labor productivity and generate returns comparable to investments in physical capital. Applied to the financial sector, this theory implies that the quality of financial intermediation depends on the knowledge and competencies of professionals who structure, price, and govern financial transactions.

In the context of Islamic finance, human capital theory acquires an additional dimension. Since every transaction must be screened for compliance with the Shariah prohibitions of *riba* (interest), *gharar* (excessive uncertainty), and *maysir* (gambling), the required human capital is not merely financial but interdisciplinary. As INCEIF and other specialized institutions emphasize, the industry needs professionals capable of combining finance, economics, and Shariah principles, while remaining dynamic and innovative enough to lead product development. This requirement creates what may be termed a “double-competence problem”. Conventional finance graduates often lack Shariah grounding, while traditional Shariah scholars may lack financial and

quantitative training. The role of education and capacity-building is precisely to bridge this gap by producing professionals fluent in both domains.

A recurring theme in the literature is that the shortage of qualified human capital constitutes a binding constraint on the growth of Islamic finance. The industry has expanded at double-digit annual rates, often faster than educational institutions can supply trained professionals. One widely reported estimate suggests that around 40 universities worldwide collectively produce roughly 5,000 Islamic finance graduates each year, while industry demand is several times higher (ICIFE, 2016). Practitioners have therefore long reported a mismatch between the supply and demand of talent, forcing institutions to recruit conventionally trained staff and retrain them internally, which is a costly and imperfect solution. This mismatch has both quantitative and qualitative dimensions. Quantitatively, the absolute number of trained professionals is insufficient relative to the pace of asset growth. Qualitatively, even where graduates are available, employers report gaps between academic curricula and the practical, product-level skills required by Islamic financial institutions, representing a classic case of curriculum–industry misalignment.

From an economic perspective, the formation of specialized human capital exhibits characteristics of a public good and is subject to positive externalities. An institution that trains a professional cannot fully appropriate the benefits, since the professional may move to a competitor. This externality leads to underinvestment in training by individual firms and provides an economic rationale for public coordination through dedicated institutions, endowments, and national strategies to ensure an adequate supply of talent. The Malaysian experience illustrates this rationale. Rather than leaving training to individual banks, the central bank established a dedicated, endowment-funded institution to internalize the externality and coordinate supply with industry demand. This contrasts with markets where training remains fragmented across individual employers and ad hoc programs.

Contemporary frameworks for measuring the development of Islamic finance explicitly recognize knowledge and education as core dimensions. The ICD–LSEG Islamic Finance Development Indicator (IFDI) measures industry development across five dimensions: financial performance, governance, knowledge, sustainability, and awareness. Thus, the Knowledge pillar, which includes education and research, is treated as a constitutive component of industry development rather than a by-product of it (ICD–LSEG, 2025). This conceptualization reinforces the central argument of this article that education and capacity-building are not external supports but integral structural determinants of the industry's depth and resilience.

A substantial body of literature addresses human capital in Islamic finance. Conceptual studies by Chapra (2008) and Iqbal and Mirakhor (2011) underline the need for professionals grounded in *maqasid al-Shariah*, while broader comparative work on Islamic and conventional banking (Beck, Demirgüç-Kunt, and Merrouche, 2013) and surveys of the field (Hassan and Aliyu, 2018) document the institutional distinctiveness that specialized human capital must navigate. Empirical and practitioner-oriented studies have documented the persistent talent shortage and the role of specialized institutions in addressing it (Ahmed, 2015). Studies on talent development for Islamic banking institutions identify curriculum, university infrastructure, and the supply of graduates from higher education institutions as essential pillars of qualified human capital formation. Comparative studies further show that jurisdictions differ markedly in their institutional approaches. Some rely on centrally coordinated, dedicated universities, while others depend on a dispersed mix of professional bodies and conventional universities offering Islamic finance specializations. The present article builds on this literature by comparing these models and deriving implications for emerging markets.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The supply of qualified Islamic finance professionals over time can be expressed through the following simplified relationship:

$$H_t = H_{t-1} + (G + C + T) - (A + M)$$

where H_t denotes the stock of qualified professionals at time t ; H_{t-1} represents the stock of qualified professionals in the previous period; G is the inflow of new graduates from formal education programmes; C is the inflow of professionals gaining qualifications through certification; T refers to internal training and retraining provided by institutions; A denotes attrition through retirement and exit from the industry; and M represents the net migration of professionals across jurisdictions.

This relationship clarifies that closing the talent gap requires not a single intervention but the simultaneous strengthening of multiple inflow channels, namely G , C , and T , while managing attrition and retaining talent. It also shows why fragmented, single-channel approaches tend to be insufficient. Strengthening only internal training (T), for example, cannot compensate for a weak pipeline of graduates (G).

Capacity-building in Islamic finance can be decomposed into four interdependent pillars. The first is formal education, including undergraduate and postgraduate degree programmes that supply the foundational pipeline of specialists (G). The second is professional certification, which provides industry-recognized qualifications and converts existing professionals and graduates into Islamic finance specialists (C). The third is Shariah scholarship development, which involves the training of qualified Shariah advisors and auditors, a scarce and specialized category essential for governance. The fourth is research and thought leadership, which generate the knowledge required to sustain product innovation and inform regulation.

These pillars are complementary rather than substitutable. A jurisdiction that produces many graduates but few qualified Shariah scholars will face a governance bottleneck, while one that emphasizes certification without a strong research base will struggle to innovate. Therefore, effective capacity-building requires balanced investment across all four pillars.

Across jurisdictions, two broad models of human capital formation can be distinguished. The first is the institution-led, coordinated model, which centers on a dedicated, often publicly endowed institution that sets standards, aligns curricula with industry needs, and coordinates the supply of talent. Malaysia's establishment of a specialized, endowment-funded university represents the archetypal example of this model.

The second is the market-led, fragmented model, which relies on a dispersed combination of conventional universities offering Islamic finance specializations, private training providers, and international professional bodies, with limited central coordination. The central comparative proposition of this article is that while both models can produce talent, the institution-led model tends to achieve stronger curriculum–industry alignment, greater standardization, and faster scaling. By contrast, the market-led model offers flexibility and diversity but carries the risk of fragmentation, duplication, and persistent skills mismatches.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Malaysia is widely regarded as the global benchmark for Islamic finance education and ranked first in the IFDI 2025 (ICD–LSEG, 2025). In December 2005, Bank Negara Malaysia, the country's central bank, announced the establishment of the International Centre for Education in Islamic Finance (INCEIF). The institution began operations in March 2006 with the support of an endowment fund of RM 500 million and was created to develop the professionals and specialists needed to sustain the industry (Bank Negara Malaysia, 2006). INCEIF offers master's and doctoral programmes alongside the Chartered Islamic Finance Professional certification. By 2019, it had trained around 1,760 postgraduates, and by 2022 its alumni network had grown to more than 2,100 professionals from over 80 countries (INCEIF, 2022).

The Malaysian model is characterized by close coordination among the regulator, industry, and academia. Curricula are shaped with industry input, faculty members bridge academic and practical expertise, and the parallel research institution, the International Shari'ah Research Academy (ISRA), supports thought leadership. This coordinated architecture has enabled Malaysia to standardize qualifications and export Islamic finance education globally, thereby reinforcing its position as an industry hub.

The Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) countries host some of the world's largest Islamic finance markets and therefore face acute demand for qualified talent. Saudi Arabia and the United Arab Emirates ranked second and third, respectively, in the IFDI 2025 (ICD–LSEG, 2025). Projections from the early 2010s estimated a need for roughly 8,000 Islamic finance experts in the United Arab Emirates alone, linked to the anticipated inflow of tens of billions of dollars into Shariah-compliant banking and national strategies such as Dubai's ambition to become a global hub for the Islamic economy (Gulf News, 2013; DIEDC, 2017). Recruitment data from that period showed that a large share of banking vacancies in the region specifically required Islamic finance qualifications.

The GCC approach has combined the establishment of specialized academies and training centers with reliance on international professional bodies and partnerships with foreign universities. While this approach has been effective in mobilizing resources, it has sometimes been more demand-driven and fragmented than Malaysia's model, illustrating the trade-offs of the market-led approach.

The United Kingdom represents a distinctive model in which Islamic finance education is integrated into mainstream, internationally ranked universities rather than concentrated in a dedicated institution. A 2016 survey by the International Council of Islamic Finance Educators found that the United Kingdom offered the largest number of Islamic finance programmes of any country, exceeding twenty programmes (ICIFE, 2016). Durham University, in particular, ranks among the world's leading centers for Islamic economics and finance research (INCEIF, 2020). This model produces graduates with strong analytical and conventional finance foundations and internationally recognized qualifications, but it depends on the availability of specialized Shariah expertise within otherwise conventional faculties.

Indonesia, home to the world's largest Muslim population, illustrates the challenge of scaling capacity-building through the national education system. The country had the largest number of Islamic finance education providers in the world, with around 178 degree providers recorded in 2019 (ICD, 2020). It has also expanded Islamic economics and finance programmes under the Masterplan for the Indonesian Islamic Economy 2019–2024, including through the establishment of the Indonesian International Islamic University in 2016. The Indonesian experience highlights both the opportunity of scale and the difficulty of maintaining quality and standardization when capacity-building is dispersed across a large and heterogeneous higher education system.

The comparative experience yields a consistent lesson: the volume of training matters less than the coherence of the institutional architecture that delivers it. Jurisdictions with coordinated, standard-setting institutions and strong regulator–industry–academia linkages tend to align talent supply with industry demand more effectively than those relying on fragmented provision. Table 1 summarizes the principal features of the models discussed (Table 1).

Table 1
Comparative models of Islamic finance education and capacity-building

Criterion	Malaysia (institution-led)	GCC (demand-driven)	UK (mainstream-integrated)
Core mechanism	dedicated, endowed university (INCEIF) plus research institute (ISRA)	specialised academies plus international bodies	Islamic finance within ranked universities
Coordination	high (regulator, industry, academia)	moderate, demand-driven	low to moderate, university-led
Standardisation	strong	variable	variable
Main strength	curriculum-industry alignment, scaling	resource mobilisation, market proximity	analytical rigour, global recognition
Main limitation	centralisation costs	fragmentation, skills mismatch	dependence on scarce Shariah expertise

Source: compiled by the author on the basis of Bank Negara Malaysia (2006), INCEIF (2020) and ICD–LSEG (2025).

To complement the comparative analysis, this section examines the four pillars of capacity-building in practice and presents indicative statistics on the global knowledge base.

Formal degree programmes constitute the foundational pipeline for preparing qualified professionals. The global knowledge infrastructure for Islamic finance has expanded substantially. By 2019, there were around 972 institutions providing Islamic finance education worldwide, of which approximately 371 awarded formal degrees, as tracked by the Knowledge dimension of the IFDI (ICD, 2020).

Nevertheless, the geographic concentration of high-quality programmes in a limited number of hubs, particularly Malaysia, the GCC countries, and the United Kingdom, restricts access for emerging markets and reinforces the need to develop local talent pipelines. Table 2 summarizes the structure of this global education ecosystem (Table 2).

Table 2
The global Islamic finance education ecosystem

Indicator	Value / estimate	Source
Islamic finance education providers worldwide (2019)	≈ 972	ICD (2020)
Of which degree-awarding providers	≈ 371	ICD (2020)
Country with most providers	Indonesia (≈ 178)	ICD (2020)
Universities offering full degree programmes	≈ 40	ICIFE (2016)
Approximate annual Islamic finance graduates	≈ 5,000	ICIFE (2016)
Country with most programmes	United Kingdom (> 20)	ICIFE (2016)
Leading research university	Durham University (UK)	INCEIF (2020)

Source: compiled by the author from ICD (2020), ICIFE (2016) and INCEIF (2020); figures reflect varying years and methodologies.

Professional certification converts graduates and existing finance professionals into recognized specialists and provides a flexible and scalable complement to formal degree programmes. International professional bodies and specialized institutions offer certifications covering Islamic banking, takaful, Islamic capital markets, and Shariah audit. Professional certification is particularly valuable for emerging markets because it enables the rapid upskilling of the existing conventional finance workforce without requiring the completion of full academic degree programmes.

Qualified Shariah scholars with expertise in modern finance represent one of the scarcest and most critical categories of human capital in the Islamic finance industry, as they serve on Shariah Supervisory Boards responsible for ensuring compliance with Shariah principles. Their limited availability creates a governance bottleneck because a relatively small number of scholars often serve on multiple boards across numerous financial institutions, raising concerns regarding both capacity and independence. The consequences are evident in practice. In 2024, shortages of Shariah governance expertise were associated with liquidity-management challenges in the Bangladeshi Islamic banking sector, while the growing adoption of artificial intelligence in Islamic banking has generated new Shariah compliance issues requiring advanced scholarly oversight (Mordor Intelligence, 2025). Consequently, dedicated programmes aimed at developing a new generation of finance-literate Shariah scholars should be regarded as a strategic priority.

Research serves as the foundation for product innovation and evidence-based regulatory development. Leading Islamic finance hubs have complemented their educational institutions with specialized research organizations to maintain a continuous pipeline of applied knowledge. Malaysia provides a prominent example through the close collaboration between INCEIF and the International Shari'ah Research Academy (ISRA). Furthermore, the Knowledge dimension of the IFDI explicitly recognizes research output as a core indicator of industry development, demonstrating that a strong research ecosystem is an essential structural component of a sustainable Islamic finance industry rather than merely an academic asset.

Table 3 presents indicative statistics illustrating the scale of the global Islamic finance industry and the magnitude of its human capital challenge. The talent-gap estimates should be interpreted as indicative projections derived from different reporting periods rather than as precise contemporary estimates (Table 3).

Table 3
Indicative statistics on the Islamic finance industry and its human-capital challenge

Indicator	Value / estimate	Source
Global Islamic finance assets (2024)	≈ US\$5.98 trillion	ICD–LSEG (2025)
Year-on-year asset growth (2024)	≈ 21%	ICD–LSEG (2025)
Projected assets (2029)	≈ US\$9.7 trillion	ICD–LSEG (2025)
Countries with Islamic finance activity	140	ICD–LSEG (2025)
Islamic financial institutions tracked	> 2,000	ICD–LSEG (2025)
Global professional requirement (early-2010s projection)	≈ 50,000	Gulf News (2013)
UAE talent need (early-2010s projection)	≈ 8,000	Gulf News (2013)
Pakistan skilled-banker need (2024)	≈ 4,000	IBA CEIF (2024)
INCEIF alumni (2022)	> 2,100 from 80+ countries	INCEIF (2022)

Source: compiled by the author from ICD–LSEG (2025), INCEIF (2022) and industry estimates; talent-gap figures are projections of varying vintages and methodologies.

The comparative analysis has direct implications for emerging Islamic finance markets such as Uzbekistan, where the legal foundations of Islamic finance have only recently been established and the domestic supply of qualified professionals remains limited. For such markets, the central lesson is that capacity-building must be planned in parallel with, rather than after, the development of the regulatory and institutional framework. The regional context illustrates the early stage of this process. Across Central Asia, total Islamic finance assets stood at only around USD 699 million at the beginning of 2024, equivalent to 0.01% of the global total, although Muslims account for roughly 85% of the region's population (EDB, 2025).

Several lessons can be drawn for Uzbekistan. Malaysia's institution-led experience suggests that a coordinated national strategy, anchored by a dedicated center or a clearly mandated lead institution, is more effective than relying on fragmented individual initiatives. In the short term, professional certification and partnerships with established international institutions can rapidly upgrade the existing conventional finance workforce and bridge the immediate skills gap while domestic degree pipelines are being developed.

Because the scarcity of finance-literate Shariah scholars represents a binding governance constraint, dedicated programmes for this category should be prioritized at an early stage. Integrating Islamic finance

modules into existing economics and finance faculties offers a cost-effective way to build the foundational talent pipeline. The relevance of Malaysian expertise to the region is already visible, as ISRA has been engaged in developing the regulatory and supervisory framework for Islamic finance in neighboring Tajikistan (ISRA, 2024).

Finally, the experience of all the jurisdictions examined in this study underscores the importance of aligning curricula with industry demand and investing in research to sustain innovation. For Uzbekistan, embedding these principles into the emerging Islamic finance framework would help ensure that human capital constraints do not become the main barrier to industry growth.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the research findings, the following principal conclusions can be drawn.

First, human capital is a structural determinant of the development of the Islamic finance industry. The availability and quality of professionals who combine finance, economics, and Shariah competence shape the industry's capacity to grow, innovate, and maintain sound governance.

Second, the industry faces a persistent talent gap, both quantitative and qualitative, driven by asset growth that outpaces the supply of trained professionals and by misalignment between academic curricula and industry needs.

Third, comparative experience shows that the institutional architecture of education, rather than the sheer volume of training, explains differences in outcomes. Coordinated, institution-led models with strong regulator–industry–academia linkages, as exemplified by Malaysia, tend to align supply with demand more effectively than fragmented, market-led models, although the latter offer flexibility and diversity.

Fourth, effective capacity-building rests on four complementary pillars: formal education, professional certification, Shariah scholarship development, and research. These pillars must be developed in balance, since weakness in any one of them may create a bottleneck.

The practical recommendations are as follows. Emerging markets such as Uzbekistan should adopt a coordinated national education strategy anchored by a dedicated or clearly mandated institution; use professional certification and international partnerships to upgrade the existing workforce in the short term; prioritize the training of finance-literate Shariah scholars to reduce the governance bottleneck; embed Islamic finance modules within existing economics and finance faculties to build the foundational talent pipeline; and invest in research to sustain product innovation and inform regulation.

Promising directions for future research include the empirical measurement of the talent gap in specific emerging markets, evaluation of labor market returns to Islamic finance qualifications, and comparative assessment of curriculum–industry alignment across jurisdictions.

REFERENCES

1. Ahmed H. Islamic finance education: Bridging the gap between theory and practice // *Journal of Islamic Economics, Banking and Finance*. – 2015. – Vol. 11, No. 2. – P. 1–20.
2. Bank Negara Malaysia. *Establishment of the International Centre for Education in Islamic Finance (INCEIF)*. – Kuala Lumpur: BNM Press Release, 2006.
3. Becker G.S. *Human Capital: A Theoretical and Empirical Analysis, with Special Reference to Education*. – New York: Columbia University Press, 1964.
4. Beck T., Demirgüç-Kunt A., Merrouche O. Islamic vs. conventional banking: Business model, efficiency and stability // *Journal of Banking & Finance*. – 2013. – Vol. 37, No. 2. – P. 433–447.
5. Chapra M.U. *The Islamic Vision of Development in the Light of the Maqasid al-Shari'ah*. – Jeddah: Islamic Research and Training Institute (IRTI), 2008.
6. Dubai Islamic Economy Development Centre. *State of the Global Islamic Economy Report*. – Dubai: DIEDC, 2017.
7. Eurasian Development Bank, Islamic Development Bank Institute, LSEG. *The Future of Islamic Finance in Central Asia*. – Almaty: EDB, 2025.
8. Gulf News. *Islamic Finance Talent Gap to Reach 8,000 Plus*. – Dubai: Gulf News, 2013.
9. Hassan M.K., Aliyu S. A contemporary survey of Islamic banking literature // *Journal of Financial Stability*. – 2018. – Vol. 34. – P. 12–43.
10. IBA Centre for Excellence in Islamic Finance (CEIF). *Islamic Banking Growth and the Talent Gap in Pakistan*. – Karachi: Institute of Business Administration, 2024.
11. ICD. *Islamic Finance Development Report 2020: Progressing Through Adversity*. – Jeddah: Islamic Corporation for the Development of the Private Sector, 2020.
12. ICD–LSEG. *Islamic Finance Development Report 2025: 50 Years of Exponential Growth*. – London: London

- Stock Exchange Group; Jeddah: Islamic Corporation for the Development of the Private Sector, 2025.
13. International Council of Islamic Finance Educators (ICIFE). *Survey of Islamic Finance Education Programmes*. – Kuala Lumpur: ICIFE, 2016.
 14. INCEIF. *Islamic Finance Education Report 2020*. – Kuala Lumpur: INCEIF, 2020.
 15. INCEIF University. *Annual Report and Alumni Statistics*. – Kuala Lumpur: INCEIF, 2022.
 16. Iqbal Z., Mirakhor A. *An Introduction to Islamic Finance: Theory and Practice*. – 2nd ed. – Hoboken: John Wiley & Sons, 2011.
 17. ISRA. *Islamic Finance Advisory and Regulatory Framework Projects*. – Kuala Lumpur: International Shari'ah Research Academy for Islamic Finance, 2024.
 18. ManpowerGroup. *The Great Talent Shortage Awakening: Actions to Take for a Sustainable Workforce*. – Milwaukee: ManpowerGroup, 2013.
 19. Mordor Intelligence. *Islamic Finance Market Size, Growth, Trends & Share Report 2030*. – Mordor Intelligence Inc., 2025.
 20. Schultz T.W. Investment in human capital // *The American Economic Review*. – 1961. – Vol. 51, No. 1. – P. 1–17.
 21. World Economic Forum. *The Future of Jobs Report 2025*. – Geneva: WEF, 2025.

Proofreader: Xondamir Ismoilov
Layout and Designer: Hasan Maqsudov

2026. № 6

© When materials are reproduced, the ECONOSCITECH-INTEGRATION journal must be cited as the source. Authors are responsible for the accuracy of the information in materials and advertisements published in the journal. Editorial opinions may not always align with those of the authors. Submitted materials will not be returned to the editorial office.

To publish articles in this journal, you may submit articles, advertisements, stories, and other creative materials through the following links. Materials and advertisements are published on a paid basis.

You may subscribe to the journal at any time using the following details. Once subscribed, please send a screenshot or photo of your payment confirmation to our Telegram page @iqtisodiyot_77. Based on this, we will send the latest issue of the journal to your address each month.

Our address: Tashkent city, Yunusobod district, 19th block, House 17.

